

Determination of Stature from the Length of Sternum Bone of Cadaver Brought to Mortuary of Civil Hospital Ahmedabad

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Abstract:

The role of Forensic anthropology to derive alternative and newer modes of identification is increasing every day. Estimation of stature is one of the important initial steps during forensic analysis of human skeletal remains. The aim of the present study was to derive a linear regression formula for estimating stature from length of the sternum. The study included 170 male & female sternums of Indian origin dissected from cadavers during medico-legal autopsies. The regression equation for both sexes was "Stature= 94.228 + 4.474 × (Combined Length of Manubrium and Body of Sternum)", with a standard error of 3.901 cm and a strength of correlation of 0.858. This early study shows that the length of the sternum can be utilized for estimating stature.

Keywords; Stature Estimation, Sternal Length, Linear Regression, Forensic Anthropology.

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Introduction

For medicolegal investigations, analysis of the human skeleton is obviously critical for identification purposes. Experts are always having difficulty determining if skeleton remains are human or not, as well as assessing the correct age, gender, and stature of the specimen provided. According to Krogman, if the entire skeleton is available for examination, sexing of the adult skeleton can be done with 100% accuracy, with the skull up to 90%, the pelvis up to 95%, the long bones up to 80%, and when available, up to 98% [1].

Wenzel [2] conducted the first study on the sternum as an individual parameter for sex determination in 1788. He explained the difference in ratio. Between the length of manubrium and the body of the sternum in both sexes. Feigal (1837) [3], Hyrtl (1788) [4], Dwight (1881) [5] Strauch (1881) [6], was followed by Patermollar (1890) [7] and Paterson (1905) [8] all benefited from the study. All of these workers investigated the old sternum characteristics as well as some new optometric parameters, but were unable to create any new ones.

Stature is one feature of an individual's physiognomy, and determining it is a crucial first step in the forensic study of skeleton remains. [9] Stature can be measured using numerous anthropometric measurements of the skeleton. Such an estimation is based on the relationship between

skeleton elements and stature. [10] The current work attempts to investigate the sternum using available sex parameters and to construct a regression method for estimating stature for both sexes separately and collectively.

The results obtained with the present parameter and those obtained with this investigation are collated and graphically shown for analysis. All measurements and indicators are statistically tested to ensure accuracy and dependability for future use.

Objective

1. Determination of stature from manubrium.
2. Determination of stature from body of sternum.
3. Determination of stature from combined length of manubrium and body of sternum.

Material and Method

Material: The present study of 170 cases was conducted at B.J. Medical College, Civil Hospital Ahmedabad during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017.

The materials for the present study consist of sternum bones obtained from the cadavers brought for the post-mortem examination at Civil Hospital, Ahmedabad after taking necessary consent from the relatives and police. The bodies that were deteriorated, burnt, maimed, or with physical

anomalies influencing the study were excluded from the study.

The body was positioned supine on a level, hard-surfaced autopsy table, knees and hips stretched, neck and feet neutral. The cadaver's length (stature) was using a measuring tape, I measured from the vertex of the head to the heel. After removing the corpse, soft tissues and muscles were removed from the bones to the greatest extent possible. The sternum bones were collected, labelled, and macerated in a sodium chloride solution for one week. These were cleaned, soft tissues were removed, and the bones were placed in a hydrogen peroxide solution to be cleaned.

The measurements were collected using Baker's Digital Calliper, which has a reading precision of 0.01mm/0.0005 inches and a range of 0-300mm/0-12 inches. A rectangular hardwood board was used; all four borders were thicker than the remainder of the board, so that while taking measures, the sternum remained in touch with two thicker borders arranged at 90 degrees to each other. This will confirm the sternum's position and ensure that it does not shift while being measured with a calliper. The sternum bone used for measuring was put on this board so

that its rear surface came into contact with the board's surface. During the examination, the hand was placed on the xiphoid region to further support this. The sternum was practically immobile during the test. After proper positioning, the following measurements were acquired with a digital calliper.

1. Manubrium length (M) refers to the distance between the suprasternal notch and sternal angle in midline.
2. Body of Sternum (B) length refers to the distance between the sternal angle and the midline junction of the sternum and xiphoid process.
3. The Combined Length of Manubrium and Body of Sternum (M+B) is the distance between the suprasternal notch, the junction of the body of sternum, and the xiphoid process in the midline.
4. Manubrio corpus index (Sternal index) = $M/B \times 100$.

The data obtained were entered, compiled and analysed using Microsoft Office Excel 2016. Descriptive and analytical statistical analysis was performed using Epi-info and M.S. Excel 2016. Correlation and regression were also performed. P-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Figure 1: Photograph Showing Baker's Digital Calliper with Features

Figure 2: Photograph showing the method of taking length of body of sternum

Result & Observation

In the present study 170 medicolegal cases were selected.

Study was carried of B.J. Medical College, Civil Hospital Ahmedabad during the period of 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017

Table 1 shows sex wise distribution of stature, which suggests that the maximum number of total cases were in range of 156-160(24%), followed by stature range of 151-155 (21%). Lowest numbers of total cases were found in range of 135-140 (1%).

Table 1: Sex Wise Distribution of the Stature

Stature (In cm.)	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
135-140	00(0%)	01(1%)	01(1%)
141-145	00(0%)	04(4%)	04(4%)
146-150	02(2%)	09(9%)	11(11%)
151-155	13(13%)	08(8%)	21(21%)
156-160	18(18%)	06(6%)	24(24%)
161-165	16(16%)	01(1%)	17(17%)
166-170	16(16%)	00(0%)	16(16%)
171-175	06(6%)	00(0%)	06(6%)
Total	71(71%)	29(29%)	100(100%)

The majority of male cases were discovered in the height range of 156-160 (18%), whereas the highest number of female cases were found in the range of 146-150 (9%). Table 2 shows descriptive data for the study sample. The mean age and size of males were higher than females. Except for two characteristics, the sterna index and the breadth index, the mean values of all parameters were higher in men than in women.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Study Sample

Parameter	Male			Female		
	Min.	Max.	Mean	Min.	Max.	Mean
Age (years)	17	80	37.94±17.47	17	70	32.37±14.67
Stature (cm.)	150	173	161.35±6.30	135	164	151±6.35
Length of Manubrium (L1)	40.55	66.87	48.60±4.97	27.04	56.72	44.41±5.89
Length of Body of Sternum (L2)	74.57	111.58	93.63±8.35	61.05	84.49	74.30±7.16
Combined length (L1+L2)	126.27	159.40	142.24±8.95	100.31	135.85	118.71±10.44
Width of manubrium (W)	42.95	66.17	54.24±5.23	41.49	64.15	50.73±7.08
Width of first sternebra (W1)	18.92	36.10	26.68±3.63	16.63	39.42	23.58±4.92
Width of third sternebra(W3)	22.37	50.55	31.91±4.84	21.29	37.25	26.98±4.16
Sternal Index	39.33	73.51	52.39±7.70	36.70	80.17	60.12±8.63
Width Index	57.151	110.94	84.63±12.60	61.94	121.51	87.46±11.62

Table 3 shows the correlation coefficient of stature of male and female individuals with all characteristics, which were found significant for all parameters ($P < 0.05$) except for the width index ($P = 0.131$).

Table 3: Level of Significance of Different Measurements for Both Sexes

	L1	L2	L1+L2	W	W1	W3	Sternal Index	Width Index
Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.451	0.815	0.858	0.300	0.236	0.359	-0.366	-0.152
P value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.018	0.000	0.000	0.131

The correlation coefficient indicates the strength of association between stature and various parameters used in present study and it varies from -1 (negative correlation) to +1 (positive correlation)

In the current study, the correlation coefficient for the combined length of manubrium and body of sternum (L1+L2) (0.858) was found to be greater than other characteristics, indicating that combined length had the strongest link with stature. Maximum strength of association of equation with the stature

was found for both sexes (0.858) followed by for male (0.832) and for female (0.650).

Discussion

The present study was performed over 170 subjects above the age of 17 years whose medico-legal autopsies were performed at B.J. Medical College of this institute from 1st February 2016 to 31st January 2017

Table 4: Comparison of Cases According to Sex Wise Distribution of Length of Manubrium (L1)

Length Of Manubrium (In mm.) (L1)	Tailor et al. [11]		Present Study	
	Male (%)	Female (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
25-30	00(0%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	01(1%)
31-35	02(1.72%)	03(2.58%)	00(0%)	01(1%)
36-39	01(0.86%)	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	02(2%)
40-43	07(6.03%)	10(8.62%)	17(17%)	09(9%)
44-47	26(22.41%)	16(13.79%)	13(13%)	09(9%)
48-51	21(18.10%)	04(3.44%)	27(27%)	06(6%)
52-55	13(11.20)	04(3.44%)	10(10%)	00(0%)
56-59	04(3.44%)	01(0.865)	02(2%)	01(1%)
60-65	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	01(1%)	00(0%)
66-70	00(0%)	00(0%)	01(1%)	00(0%)
Total	76	40	71	29

In present study maximum number of male cases (27%) were falling in the range of 48-51mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [11] maximum male cases (22.41%) were falling in range of 44-47mm. In present study maximum number of female cases (9%) were falling in two different ranges i.e. 40-43mm. and 44-47mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [11] maximum number of female cases (13.79%) were falling in range of 44-47mm.

Table 5: Comparison of Cases According To Sex Wise Distribution of Length of Body of Sternum (L2)

Length Of Body of Sternum (In mm.) (L2)	Tailor et al. [11]		Present Study	
	Male (%)	Female (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
56-59	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	00(0%)
60-63	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	04(4%)
64-67	01(0.86%)	03(2.58%)	00(0%)	00(0%)
68-71	01(0.86%)	09(7.75%)	00(0%)	09(9%)
72-75	04(3.44%)	02(1.72%)	01(1%)	03(3%)
76-79	06(5.17%)	09(7.75%)	00(0%)	06(6%)
80-83	11(9.48%)	09(7.75%)	09(9%)	04(4%)
84-87	07(6.03%)	00(0%)	09(9%)	03(3%)
88-91	14(12.06%)	07(6.03%)	15(15%)	00(0%)
92-95	09(7.75%)	00(0%)	12(12%)	00(0%)
96-99	06(5.17%)	00(0%)	07(7%)	00(0%)
100-103	13(11.20%)	00(0%)	09(9%)	00(0%)
104-107	01(0.86%)	01(0.86%)	05(5%)	00(0%)
108-115	00(0%)	00(0%)	04(4%)	00(0%)
Total	76	40	71	29

In present study maximum number of male cases (15%) were falling in the range of 88-91mm. which was similar to study of Tailor et al. [11] where maximum cases (12.06%) were falling in same range. In present study maximum number of female

cases (9%) were falling in range of 68-71mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [11] maximum number of female cases (7.75%) were falling in three different ranges i.e. 68-71mm, 76-mm., and 80-83mm.

Table 6: Comparison of Cases According to Sex Wise Distribution of Combined Length of Manubrium and Body of Sternum (L1+L2)

Combined Length (L1+L2)	Tailor et al. [11]		Present Study	
	Male (%)	Female (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
101-104	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	00(0%)	04(4%)
105-108	00(0%)	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	01(1%)
109-112	02(1.72%)	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	05(5%)
113-116	00(0%)	09(7.75%)	00(0%)	02(2%)
117-120	01(0.86%)	07(6.03%)	00(0%)	06(6%)
121-124	06(5.17%)	10(8.62%)	00(0%)	01(1%)
125-128	12(10.34%)	03(2.58%)	02(2%)	03(3%)
129-132	08(6.89%)	02(1.72%)	13(13%)	05(5%)
133-136	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	10(10%)	02(2%)
137-140	09(7.75%)	02(1.72%)	08(8%)	00(0%)
141-144	11(9.48%)	03(2.58%)	06(6%)	00(0%)
145-148	07(6.03%)	00(0%)	12(12%)	00(0%)
149-152	07(6.03%)	00(0%)	10(10%)	00(0%)
153-156	06(5.17%)	00(0%)	09(9%)	00(0%)
157-160	02(1.72%)	00(0%)	01(1%)	00(0%)
161-164	01(0.86%)	01(0.86%)	00(0%)	00(0%)
Total	76	40	71	29

In present study maximum numbers of male cases (13%) were falling in the range of 129-132mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [11] maximum numbers of male cases (10.34%) were falling in range of 125-128mm. In present study maximum numbers of female cases (6%) were falling in range of 117-120mm. while in study of Tailor et al. [11] maximum numbers of female cases (8.62%) were falling in range of 121-124mm.

In present study the regression equation for determination of stature of male from combined length was $S=78.027+(0.586) \times \text{Combined Length of manubrium and body of sternum}$. The strength of association was 0.832.

The standard error of the estimate was 6.706 cm. The results derived from the present study were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). These results were comparable with the study of Menezes et al. [12] He derived regression equation, s Stature = $117.784 + (3.429 \times \text{Sternal length})$ where standard error of estimate was 5.64cm and correlation coefficient was 0.638 with significant p value ($p \leq 0.001$).

Summary and Conclusion

- Regression equation derived for both sexes collectively was “Stature= $94.228 + 4.474 \times (\text{Combined Length of manubrium and body of sternum})$ ”, with Standard Error=3.901cm and strength of association=0.858.
- Regression equation derived for male sex was “Stature= $78.027+(0.586) \times (\text{combined length of manubrium and body of sternum})$ ”, with

Standard Error=6.706cm and strength of association=0.832.

- Regression equation derived for female sex was “Stature= $104.07 + (0.395) \times (\text{Combined Length of manubrium and body of sternum})$ ”, with Standard Error=10.612cm and strength of association=0.650.

So, it is evident from the above findings that out of all the parameters used in the study for determination of sex, length of body of sternum and combined length of manubrium and body of sternum are reliable. All the other parameters are not reliable for sex determination.

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